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Review Article

**REVIEW ON THE USE OF NANO-CARRIERS FOR THE
TREATMENT OF NEURO DEGENERATIVE DISORDERS**

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Article Received: May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

NDs have become a serious health problem to wide population of the world. Presently there is no cure available for most of the NDs. The current therapies for NDs focused on modifying the disease progression and symptoms. Nanometric drug delivery is a promising technique that can be employed to deliver the drug to the brain which can be accomplished through nasal cavity. Primary obstacle for the effective treatment of NDs is the presence of blood-brain barrier (BBB), which limits or prevents the drug from reaching the central nervous system (CNS). The development of nanotechnology through integrated multidisciplinary efforts, will result in novel insights into the functions of neural circuits and approaches for the diagnostic and therapy of brain diseases. The majority of nanotechnological drug delivery systems for the treatment of Neurodegenerative Diseases are in the form of polymeric nanoparticles. Polymeric nanoparticles can pass through the tight junctions, cross the BBB then achieve a high drug loading capacity and targeted the mutagenic proteins in neuro degenerative disease. This article discuss about the various neurodegenerative disorders, the method of targeting the diseases and the techniques to fabricate the formulations that can target the neuro-degenerative diseases.

Keywords: Neuro degenerative disease, blood brain barrier, Nano carrier**Corresponding author:****Sumitha M Das,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The recent decades have seen a remarkable hike in the prevalence of neurodegenerative diseases (NDs). NDs have become a genuine medical issue to wide population of the world. Presently there is no fix accessible for most of the NDs. The current therapies for NDs focused on modifying the disease progression and symptoms. This treatment regimen is not effective in improving the condition of the disease [1]. Primary obstacle for the effective treatment of NDs is the attendance of blood-brain barrier (BBB), which limits or prevents the drug from reaching the central nervous system (CNS). This impediment is seen because of the capacity of the BBB in keeping up CNS homeostasis and forestalling the free dissemination and infiltration of most medications and other remote segments from the circulation system to the brain [2].

CNS disorders create lot of emotional, economic and social weight to the patients their families and to the society. Even the present communities consider the CNS disorders as the “disease of the mind”. [3] CNS conveyance of medication are important for the treatments of these disorders. There are lot of hurdle in the innovative work of new medications for the therapy of CNS issue, beginning from

pathophysiology of brain disorder, the trouble in getting to the mind with both micro and macromolecule medications, to the hazard, intricacy and extensive costs of the clinical preliminaries required for regulatory approval. [4] These hurdles have resulted in reduced effort from pharmaceutical industries in developing drugs for the treatment of many CNS disorders.

Over the last few years to overcome the difficulties related with the release of the drugs to the brain the pharma industries are concentrating on new technologies for bypassing the hurdles like BBB [5]. Nanometric drug delivery is a promising technique that can be implemented to deliver the drug to the brain which can be accomplished through nasal cavity. The second-generation nano lipid carriers, nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) which is an improved version derived from solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) can be considered as the first choice carrier for the nose to brain release of the drug to the brain. NLCs are typically composed of biodegradable and biocompatible lipid components basically formed from indigenous sources. Besides, nanostructured lipid carriers offer high drug ensnarement efficiencies and high stability, and they have an entrenched safety profile and toxicological information. [6]

FIGURE: 1 OVERALL SCOPE OF NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASE

Neurodegenerative diseases

Diseases of the brain can be divided into three main classes, namely the neurodegenerative diseases, neuroinflammatory diseases, and neoplastic diseases. Neurodegenerative disorders includes different types of conditions which are either sporadic or familial or both and their common cause is the continual loss of neuronal subtypes. APHD are known as the most widely recognized neurodegenerative diseases. [7]

The range of disorders of the brain is relatively large, covering many clutters that are recorded in either the psychological or neurological disorder parts of the established international diagnostic grouping systems. These disorders have a high prevalence just as short- and long-term impairments and disabilities. [8] Hence, they are an enthusiastic, economic and social burden to the patients, their families and their social status. Only within the group of neurodegenerative disease includes serious disorders such as AD, PD, Lewy body dementia (LBD), frontotemporal dementia (FTD), vascular dementia (VD) and some rare disorders such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), Huntington disease (HD), spinocerebellar ataxia and prion diseases. Regardless of the significant contrasts in clinical indication, neurodegenerative disorders share general features, for example, their appearance late in life, the extensive neuronal damage and

synaptic deformities, and the presence of cerebral deposits of misfolded proteins aggregates.

Approximately 24 million people overall experience the effects of dementia, 60% of cases being because of AD, which happens in 1% of individuals aged 50 to 70 and significantly increases to 50% for those over 70 years.[9] Dramatically, these numbers are evaluated to increment to 15 million in the following 40 years.

Many studies have reported the impact of neurodegenerative diseases on the BBBs, most plausibly through neuro-inflammation.[7] Changes to the BBB not only prevent it from performing its normal functions, such as transporting nutrients, its role as a signaling interface, improving immune cell passage, and maintaining homeostasis, but also hinder the transport of drugs to the CNS to manage neurodegeneration. The adopted notion is that the Blood Brain Barrier is a static element, i.e., immune to brain changes. [10]

Neurodegenerative diseases are usually related with neuronal loss and cell death. The neurons that survive exhibit changes in nuclear defragmentation, size, shape, chromatin condensation among other morphological changes. Neurodegeneration occurs when neurons cannot terminate the apoptotic phase due, thus becoming inflamed and necrotic. [9]

FIGURE: 2 CAUSES, SYMPTOMS AND GENERAL TREATMENT FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASE

Blood-brain barrier

Blood brain barrier is the part of central nervous system, which having a well-developed structure. BBB is present in the brain and spinal cord in all mammals. The BBB is a highly selective semipermeable membrane that separates the circulating blood from cerebrospinal fluid. BBB is a specialized structure responsible for the protection of the brain from circulating toxins and cells through a selective permeability system. [11] BBB is formed by cerebral microvasculature endothelial cells, which, along with astrocytes, pericytes, neurons, and the extracellular matrix. It provides average surface area of about 12–18 m² for a human adult. [4]

BBB consist of tight junctions formed by cerebral endothelial cells, the choroid plexus, epithelial cells and the cells of the arachnoid epithelium.

BBB Permeation Mechanisms

There are various potential routes for permeation across the BBB are shown in (fig. 3) some hydrophilic and lipophilic particles can enter the brain by paracellular and transcellular diffusion. Other substances, incorporate amino acids, peptides and nucleosides, may enter the brain through carrier-mediated transport, receptor-mediated transcytosis and/or adsorptive-mediated transcytosis. [12,13]

The various mechanisms to transport the molecules across the BBB involve the following:[14]

1. **Diffusion:** most of the lipophilic and low molecular weight molecules(500Da) can transport passively through BBB.
2. **Paracellular diffusional pathways:** Blood Brain Barrier disruption due to local inflammation by CNS and circulatory variables leads to weakening of the tight intersection, which permits the entry of polar solutes between the endothelial cells from blood vessels to brain extracellular fluid. [15]
3. **Carrier-mediated transport:** tiny molecules such as ions, glucose and amino acids that cannot pass through the cell membrane, they can be transferred to brain from blood vessels through carrier-mediated influx.[16]
4. **Receptor-mediated transcytosis:** Some of the macromolecules such as hormones and proteins can be transported by the specific receptors, exhibit on the luminal side of the endothelial cells, in the brain parenchyma
5. **Adsorptive transcytosis:** The positively charged molecules attract with the negatively charged plasma membrane, thereby initiating endocytosis which prompts to transcytosis.

FIGURE: 3 PATHWAYS FOR BBB PENETRATION

Nanotechnology approaches to penetrate the BBB

The invention of nanotechnology included multidisciplinary efforts will result in novel insights into the elements of neural circuits and approaches for the diagnostic and therapy of brain diseases. Nanotechnology based delivery systems can affect the drug capability to pass the biological barrier then targeting drugs to specific molecular targets and effectively delivering drugs to specific sites of action.[17]

Most of nanotechnological drug delivery systems for the treatment of Neurodegenerative Disorders are as polymeric nanoparticles. Polymeric nanoparticles can pass through the tight junctions, cross the BBB then accomplish a high drug loading capacity and targeted the mutagenic proteins in neuro degenerative disease. These nanosystems targeted the CNS delivery are:[18]

- Chemical properties can be easily achieve organ based on both specific and non-specific mechanism
- The targeted delivery of drugs can be controlled
- They increase the bioavailability and efficacy of incorporated medications by masking the physicochemical attributes in this way upgraded the exchange of medicaments across BBB and protect the drugs against enzymatic degradation.

The particular properties of nanomaterials, for example, reduced size, biocompatibility, prolonged blood circulation, and non-toxicity, have been exploited for the production of an emerging delivery platform that can easily transfer therapeutic agents to the brain.[19]

Nanotechnology

In the recent years, the incidental growth of research and applications in the field of nanotechnology. There is an increasing optimism nanotechnology, as applied to the biomedicine will bring significant advances in the diagnosis and treatment of disease. The current advances in nanotechnology can

provide a solution to overcome the future diagnostic and new neuro therapeutic challenges for the neurodegenerative diseases.[20] Nanodrug delivery system are promising in targeting drugs to specific molecular moieties and safely delivering drugs to the specific sites of action. The sustained release of nano-drug delivery system enhanced the bioavailability and kinetic profiles of the loaded drugs, thereby minimizing the dosage regimen. Thus, the overall effectiveness of drug candidate can be enhanced by adopting the nanotechnology in the therapeutics.[21,22,23]

Nanoparticles are colloidal matrix like system with compact structure where the drug candidate is incorporated within the colloid matrix and these are considered to be a sustained or controlled release drug delivery in biological systems.[24] Nanoparticles are generally regarded as carriers with size smaller than 100nm and more suitable for the drug delivery and targeting. They exist in either crystalline or amorphous form have high cellular uptake as compared to microparticle due to their small size and mobility. Nanoparticles are commonly made up of polymers and lipids and have unique features such as fluorescence properties, ability to absorb and transport various substances such as drugs, proteins and probes.[25]

Many challenges must be overcome if the application of nanotechnology is to realize the anticipated improved understanding of the pathophysiological basis of disease, bring more sophisticated diagnostic opportunities, and yield improved therapies.[26]

The advantages of using nanoparticles loaded with drugs, because of their small size can enter through small capillaries and are taken up by cells and allow the drug release at right rate and dose at specific sites in the body for a certain time to release the accurate delivery, which enhances the therapeutic effect and reduces the toxicity and side effects. The use of biodegradable resources for nanoparticles preparation allows sustained release within the target site over a period of days or even weeks.[27]

TABLE: 1 OUTLINE OF NANOPARTICLES AND ITS APPLICATIONS

Particles class	Materials	application
Natural material	Chitosan	Drug and gene delivery
	Dextran	Drug and gene delivery
	Gelatin	Drug and gene delivery
	Alginate	Drug and gene delivery
	Liposomes	Drug and gene delivery
	Starch	Drug and gene delivery
Dendrimers	Branched polymers	Drug delivery
Fullerenes	Carbon based nanotubes	Photodynamics and drug delivery
Ferrofluids	SPIONS	Imaging by MRI

Quantum dots	Cd/Zn selenides	Imaging and diagnostics
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An effective Nanocarrier to cross BBB should have the following characteristic features:^[28]

- The size of the particles should be smaller than 100nm
- The synthesized particles should be nontoxic, biodegradable and biocompatible.
- Physical Stability in blood
- It must be targeting BBB and brain delivery
- Reticuloendothelial entry should be avoided.
- No aggregation of platelet
- Possible modulation of drug release profiles
- It should be scalable and cost effective manufacturing process

There are several types of nanoparticles have been developed to treat and diagnose the neuro degenerative disease.

Types of NPS as carrier for drug & diagnostic agents

- Polymeric Nanoparticles
- Nanosuspension and nanocrystals
- Polymeric micelles
- Ceramic Nanoparticles
- Liposome's
- Fullerenes and dendrimers
- SLN (Solid lipid nanoparticles)
- Magnetic nanoparticles
- Nanoshells coated with gold
- Nanomers and carbon nanotubes

Polymeric nanoparticles

Polymeric nanoparticles are solid colloidal matrix like structure with size range 1 to 100nm. They are composed of biodegradable or biocompatible polymer where the drug can be entrapped or encapsulated within the carrier. Polymeric nanoparticles have been extensively discovered in medicine because of their biocompatibility, biodegradation and low toxicity.^[29]

As nanoparticles have reasonable properties for drug delivery, for example, controlled drug release and focusing on proficiency, they have been comprehensively used to the improvement of drug delivery transporters to cross BBB..^[30]

Liposomes

Liposomes are most widely used as nanocarriers. There are small vesicles of unilamellar or multilamellar phospholipids/lipid bilayers surrounding central aqueous compartments.

Liposomes with structure like cell layer are biodegradable colloids and can be utilized to convey a wide scope of hydrophobic and hydrophilic pharmaceuticals, for example, small particles, peptides, proteins and RNAs, without changing their capacity and ensuring them against degradation and potential safe reactions.^[31] Its unique phospholipid structure which is similar to physiological barrier had made it simpler to penetrate BBB and helps therapeutic molecules to the brain.^[32] Limitations of liposomes include fast systemic elimination, quick metabolic degradation of the phospholipids, stability issues after extended storage and their inability to provide sustained release of drugs and moderately efficient for the entrapment of lipophilic compounds.^[33]

Polymeric micelles

Polymeric micelles as drug delivery systems are formed by amphiphilic copolymers having an A-B

diblock structure with A, the hydrophilic (shell) and B, the hydrophobic polymers (core).

The polymeric micelles are thermodynamically and kinetically stable in aqueous media.^[34]

Nanomicelles have natural advantage in controllable size and shape, and high en- capsulation efficiency and loading capacity. The mechanism includes the self-assembly of amphiphilic molecules, with the hydrophilic/polar area, known as the head, confronting the outside surface and the hydrophobic/non polar locale, known as the tail, shaping the core..^[35]

Dendrimers

Dendrimers are a class of counterfeit macromolecules, with a tree-like topology, depicted by defined molecular weights and specific epitome properties. The globular structure of dendrimers envelops a center, layers of extended recurrent components rising up out of the center, and useful end bunches outwardly layer.^[36]

Dendrimers can be used to focus the brain, which can be accomplished in their structure, lesser nanometric size range, and functional advantages. Dendrimers have many surface sets that can be exploited and used to conjugate multifunctional ligands. Another benefit is that medications can be captured in the spaces present in dendrimers, in this way enabling the protection of the drugs from the external environment.^[37]

Inorganic nanoparticles

Inorganic nanomaterials have been broadly utilized in biomedical applications. In any case, since they come up short on the property of biodegradability, most applications point the tissue bioimaging for diagnostics. Regardless, a few inorganic nanoparticles, including gold and silica nanoparticles, and carbon nanotubes have been utilized to convey specific drugs over the blood-brain barrier.

Gold nanoparticles

Gold nanoparticles have been normally analyzed in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases through the functionalization with therapeutic macromolecules.^[38] The treatment of Alzheimer's disease by utilizing gold nanoparticles functionalized with β -amyloid specific peptides and the treatment of Parkinson's with L-DOPA

functionalized multi-spread nanoflower-like gold nanoparticles have been considered, indicating upgraded blood-mind boundary porousness across in vitro models..^[39] AuNPs also have advantage in imaging.

Silica nanoparticles

Silica nanoparticles (SiO₂ -NPs) were widely applied in diagnosis, imaging, and drug delivery of central nervous diseases. Surface modified fluorescent silica nanoparticle subordinates have demonstrated potential for applying them as nano-vehicles for drug delivery to the brain considering about connecting different kinds of particles profoundly.^[40] By joining lactoferrin on the outside of the polyethylene glycol-covered silica nanoparticles, the procedure of receptor-intervened transcytosis of these nanosystems has been upgraded, with a most extreme vehicle efficiency watched for nanoparticles with 25 nm in diameter..^[41]

Solid lipid nanoparticle

Strong lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) rose in 1991 with the target to give biocompatibility, stockpiling dependability and to keep the incorporated medication from degradation.^[42] SLNs, colloidal transporters of nanoscopic size (50–1000 nm), comprised of strong lipids (high liquefying fat matrix), are created to vanquish the weaknesses of customary colloidal bearers, as polymeric nanoparticles and liposome.^[43] Furthermore, drug release from these nanoparticles can be controlled and can last for months due to their excellent drug entrapment ability and stability.

Nanotechnology in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases

1. Nanocarriers in Alzheimer's disease^[44,45,46]

Currently, 24 million peoples are affected by the Alzheimer's disease, which is a progressive ND characterized by memory and cognitive dysfunction. The neuropathological condition mainly occurs due to the accumulation of amyloid plaque caused by A β protein aggregation and due to the presence of intracellular neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) which are formed as a result of aggregation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein.

TABLE: 2 A LIST OF FEW POTENTIAL NANO-DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS INVESTIGATED IN THE FIELD OF AD THERAPEUTICS

Nanodrug-delivery systems	Carrier material	Active drug candidate	Molecular targets
Carbon nano tubes (CNT)	Pristine Multi-walled (MW)CNTs; Phospholipids And polysorbates	Berberine	BBB transcyto-sisCholinergic systems

Dendrimers	Hydrophobic pyridylphenylenedendrimers	o-phenylenediamine	Amyloid cascades
Gold (Au) NPs	AuNPs of 5 nm with PEG	Anthocyan-in	Amyloid cascades and tauhyperphos-phorylation
Gold (Au) NPs	Gold colloids – rods (AuNR)and spheres (AuNS)	CLPFFD peptide	Amyloid cascades
Liposome NPs	PLGA [Poly (lactic-co-glycolicacid)] functionalized with anti-transferrin receptor monoclonal antibody (OX26)and anti-A β	Peptide iA β 5	BBB transcytosis, Amyloidcascades
Liposome NPs	Cholesterol, soybean phosphatidyl-choline-functionalizedwith surface wheat germ agglutinin (WGA) and Cardioliipin (CL)	Curcumin and nerve growth factor	BBB transcytosis, Amyloidcascades and tauhyperphos-phorylation
Mesopor-oussilica NPs(MSN)	N-Cetyltrimethyl ammoniumbromide – functionalizedwith succinic anhydride (S) and 3-aminopropyltriethoxy-silane (A)	Rivastigmi-ne hydrogen tartrate (RT)	Neuronal cell death/Cholinergic systems
Mesopor-ous silica NPs (MSN)	N-Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, Tetraethoxysi-lanefunctionalized with gold(Au) nanoparticle	Metal chelator CQ (5-chloro-4-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline)	BBB transcytosis, Amyloidcascades
Polymeric NPs	Dendrigraft poly-l-lysines andpolyethelene glycol (PEG)	RVG29 peptide and BACE1-AS shRNA gene	Amyloid cascades and tautangles
Polymeric NPs	Chitosan	Piperine	Cholinergic and oxidativestress systems
Polymeric NPs	Glycidyl methacrylate	Iminodiace-tic acid (IDA)	Amyloid cascades
Metallic NPs	Iron crystal structure;functionalized with PEG	Iron oxide	Amyloid cascades
Solid Lipid NPs (SLNs)	Lipids and chitosan	RVG-9R/BACE1 siRNA	Amyloid cascades
Solid Lipid NPs (SLNs)	Cetylpalmitate and functionalized with monoclonal antibody (OX26 mA β)	Resveratrol /grape seedextract	BBB transcytosis andAmyloid cascades
Solid lipid NPs (SLNs)	Glyceryl behenate lipids	Galantami-ne hydrobrom-ide	Cholinergic systems
Solid lipid NPs (SLNs)	Heparin-conjugated stearic acid; stearylamine-cationiclipid; esterquat 1	Nerve growth factor (NGF)	Neuronal cell death
Solid lipid NPs (SLNs)	Cetyl palmitate	Rapamycin (Rp)	Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) signaling pathway

2. Nanocarriers in Parkinson's disease [47,48,49]

PD is a progressive neurological condition affecting 1–2% of the population over the age of 65, marked by loss of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, causing difficulties in the control of movements.[112]The formation and accumulation of Lewy bodies (cytoplasmic eosinophilic inclusions) made of a protein termed as α -synuclein are observed in most neuronal populations in PD patients. Levodopa

is also an efficient drug commonly used in the treatment of PD. However, it may cause long-term side effects.[113]

Nowadays, the goal of treatment is to reduce symptoms and to allow a person to function normally, and with as few side effects, as possible. Nanomaterials can be used as a tool to advance treatment of parkinson's disease through exact control of biological systems. For instances, nanotechnology may vitally advance neuroprotection in parkinson's disease.

Drug candidate	Nano drug delivery system	Carrier material	Result
Levodopa	Liposome	Chlorotoxin-modified stealth liposomes	The <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> results showed good correlation with both proved the hypothesis that CITx -LS may be a potential active targeting system to enhance the drug delivery into the brain to achieve a better PD therapy
Non-Fe hemin (NFH)	Metallic NPs	TAT-NFH-nBSA	The therapeutic nanoparticles TAT-NFH-nBSA could efficiently accumulate in the brain and produce a powerful neuroprotective effect both <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> for PD treatment.
Schisantherin A(SA)	Polymeric NPs	mPEG-PLGA nanoparticles	Brain delivery of SA was much more effective with SA-NPs than with SA suspension. In addition, the SA-NPs exerted strong neuroprotective effects
Coenzyme Q10	Nano micelle	PEG-derivatized atocopherol (PTS) micells	Study revealed that Ubisol-Q10 intervention could stop, but not reverse, the on-going neurodegeneration in MPTP-treated mouse brain

3. Nanocarriers in Huntington's disease [50,51]

HD is a neurodegenerative disease that mainly affects the cortical neurons and striatal medium spiny neurons (composed by GABAergic neuron). Almost 40% of the patients diagnosed with the disease suffer from depression, and the disease is often mistaken with schizophrenia because of their shared symptoms. Similarly, to Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease, nanocarriers can be used as a tool to deliver drugs and therapeutics across the BBB to treat Huntington's disease.

Nano drug delivery system	Drug candidate	Carrier material	Model of use
Liposomes	Curcumin	(ApoE)-derived peptides-nanoliposomes	Rat brain endothelial cell line
Nanoparticle	Trehalose	Zwitterionic poly(trehalose) nanoparticles	Transgenic mice for HD
Nanopartilce		Poly(trehalose) Nanoparticles	HD transgenic mouse
Exosomes	HEK 293 cells	miR-124	R6/2 line of transgenic HD mice
Exosomes	Glioblastoma U87 cells	Hydrophobically modified siRNAs	Wild-type FVBNj mice

CONCLUSION:

The application of NPs in the therapeutics and diagnostics appears to be promising methodology in recent years. Nanotechnology has proven to have great potential for providing neurotherapeutic modalities to limit and reverse the neuropathology of AD and PD by supporting and promoting functional regeneration of damaged neurons, providing neuroprotection, and facilitating the delivery of neuroactives such as drugs, genes, and cells across the BBB. Overall, nanocarriers can provide promising opportunities for improving neurodegenerative diseases. Nanocarriers such as liposomes, nanoparticles, nanomicelles and

exosomes, were modified in the surface to enhance brain targeting ability. The main challenges for nanoparticles used for this purpose, especially when targeting the brain, are biodegradability, biocompatibility, and non-toxicity. Another limitation that needs to be overcome is the low encapsulation efficiency of some drugs. Non-biodegradable nanoparticles can accumulate in the brain and turn into toxic substances, thus resulting in complications. Due to the limited data available from *in vivo* and clinical studies regarding the use of nanoparticles for drug delivery into the CNS, potential toxic side effects are still unknown. Therefore, the exponential growth of

nanotechnologies, novel tools will emerge, triggering the development of new insights in ND treatment and diagnosis.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The author(s) confirm that this article content has no conflict of interest.

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